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INVESTIGATION OF THE PROCESS OF ALKYLATION OF ISOBUTANE BY BUTYLENES ON ZEOLITES

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Annotation: The process of alkylation of isobutane by butylenes occupies an important place in the petrochemical and oil refining industry as a way to obtain high-octane additives to motor fuels. Currently, hydrofluoric acid or sulphuric acid is used as an alkylation catalyst, which results in large quantities of waste that are difficult to dispose of. The implementation of the process on solid catalysts has significant advantages, but such a process is complicated by the course of a polymerization side reaction and, as a result, a rapid loss of catalyst activity, so the development of new highly efficient catalysts characterized by high stability is a particularly urgent task.

Keywords: alkylation of isobutane with butylenes

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРОЦЕССА АЛКИЛИРОВАНИЯ ИЗОБУТАНА БУТИЛЕНАМИ НА ЦЕОЛИТАХ

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Аннотация: Процесс алкилирования изобутана бутиленами занимает важное место в нефтехимической и нефтеперерабатывающей

промышленности как способ получения высокооктановых присадок к моторным топливам. В настоящее время в качестве катализатора алкилирования используется плавиковая или серная кислота, в результате чего образуется большое количество отходов, которые трудно утилизировать. Реализация процесса на твердых катализаторах имеет значительные преимущества, однако такой процесс осложнен протеканием побочной реакции полимеризации и, как следствие, быстрой потерей активности катализатора, поэтому разработка новых высокоэффективных катализаторов, характеризующихся высокой стабильностью является особенно актуальной задачей.

Ключевые слова: алкилирования изобутана бутиленами

Introduction

Cation-exchange forms of zeolites of the fojasite type are very promising as such catalysts. To study the effect of the ratio of $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, samples of zeolite catalysts were prepared, in which this value was 2.5 to 5.8, i.e. it was optimal in terms of cationic composition. An increase in the silicate modulus within these limits does not have a significant effect on the catalytic properties in the alkylation reaction, although there is a tendency for more intensive formation of unsaturated compounds in the presence of cation-exchange forms of type U zeolites compared to their analogues of structure X.

Therefore, more preferable zeolite catalysts for the process under study may be contacts derived from X-type zeolites, the structure of which allows for more uniformly acidic Lewis and Brønsted centers [1].

When studying the catalytic properties of zeolite catalysts containing various cations, it was found that the introduction of calcium and ammonium into NaX zeolite leads to the appearance of catalytic activity, which increases with an increase in the degree of ion exchange (Table 1), but the content of unsaturated hydrocarbons in alkylates obtained at these catalysts is high. In addition, alkylate is characterized by a high content of hydrocarbons_{C9}. The introduction of lanthanum into the sample has a stronger effect on catalytic activity than the administration of the same amount of calcium and ammonium [2].

An increase in the lanthanum content leads to an increase in the selectivity of the process. If the substitution of calcium for ammonium does not improve the catalytic properties, then the substitution of the same amount of

calcium with lanthanum leads to a sharp increase in the activity and selectivity of the catalyst. Consequently, lanthanum occupies a special position, since its introduction into zeolite imparts to the latter a high catalytic activity in the alkylation reaction [3].

Table 1 – Studying the catalytic properties of zeolite catalysts containing various cations

Number Sample	Cationic composition	Composition of the saturated part of alkylate, %		
		C ₈	C ₉	TMP+DMG
1	CaNaX	54,4	37,6	8,9
2	LaNaX	72,7	24,9	2,4
3	NH ₄ NaX	44,5	28,3	27,2
4	NH ₄ OCaNaX	48,1	48,4	7,7
5	LaOCaNaX	87,2	87,2	21,5

Experimental part

Studies have shown that the order in which cations are introduced into the polycationic form of zeolite has a significant impact on the formation of its catalytic activity (Table 2).

Thus, the introduction of calcium into LaNaX reduces the catalytic properties, bringing them closer to the activity of CaNaX. This is confirmed by the results of IR spectral studies.

The introduction of ammonium into Ca LaNaX results in an increase in selectivity with a slight increase in activity.

The introduction of lanthanum into the ammonium form is also accompanied by a sharp increase in the activity and selectivity of the catalyst [4].

Modification of this sample with calcium results in reduced catalytic activity. There is no significant improvement in the process parameters in the case of the sample obtained by introducing calcium cation into the ammonium form. A sharp improvement in the performance of the process occurs only after the modification of the ammonium calcium form with lanthanum.

Table 2 shows that the following order of introduction of cations into zeolite is the most effective: Ca⁺, La³⁺, NH₄⁺.

Table 2 – The most effective order for introducing cations into zeolite is: Ca⁺, La³⁺, NH₄⁺.

Sample Number	Cationic composition	Composition of the saturated part of alkylate, %		
		C ₈	C ₉	TMP+DMG
1	NaX	86,9	2,4	27,2
2	NH ₄ NaX	48,6	44,4	7,7
3	LaONH ₄ NaX	87,1	3,8	8,0
4	CaONH ₄ NaX	89,9	1,8	9,1
5	CaNaX	54,4	37,6	8,9
6	LaOCaNaX	87,3	6,3	6,4
7	NH ₄ OLaCaNaX	91,2	1,1	7,7

The study of the process of thermal activation of a catalyst of optimal cationic composition has shown that the highest quality alkylate in its presence is formed only under the condition of activation at a temperature of 650 K. An increase or decrease in temperature leads to a significant deterioration in the quality of alkylate.

The results obtained give us grounds to believe that the active site in the alkylation reaction is the superpositions of the Bronsted and Lewis centers realized in zeolites with a small silicate modulus.

Despite its high activity and selectivity, the catalyst of optimal cationic composition has low stability of operation, and its original activity is not restored in the process of oxidative regeneration. Positive results were obtained by introducing metals of variable valence Pd, Mn, Mo, Co, Cr. It was found that the highest yield of target products with a low content of unsaturated compounds is characterized by molybdenum and palladium-containing samples, and the duration of their operation increases by more than 1.5 times.

The introduced metal of variable valence made it possible to reduce the regeneration temperature by 100 – 200 K.

Alkylation of isobutane by butylenes is a liquid-phase process. The pressure in the system is usually maintained so as to ensure that the reacting components remain in the reaction zone in the liquid phase. As you know, this condition is fulfilled after the saturation pressure of the components is reached. Thermodynamically, the fluid is identical to its equilibrium saturated vapor. From a thermodynamic point of view, the creation of reactant pressures that exceed saturation pressures at a given temperature is unjustified [5].

As noted, alkylation processes are carried out at relatively low temperatures (5-10°C and 30-35°C when H₂SO₄ HF is used, respectively). The optimal temperatures of the zeolite catalyst alkylation process depend on the nature of the catalyst. The temperature regimes indicated in the literature range from 40 to 135°C.

In this regard, it was necessary to study the effect of the alkylation temperature on the performance of the process in the presence of the optimal zeolite catalyst described above.

Figure 1 shows the test results of this catalyst in the temperature range of 25-100°C (volumetric butylene feed rate 0.1h-1). From Fig. Figure 1 shows a clear maximum on the yield curve and a less obvious minimum of unsaturated hydrocarbons in the alkylate at 80°C.

Figure 1 – Effect of alkylation temperature on alkylate yields (C₈ fraction) and carbohydrates C₉ and higher

We studied the effect of the isobutane:butylene ratio on the performance of the alkylation process in the range of ratios from 7:1 to 100:1.

Figure 2. The results are presented: With an increase in the ratio of isobutane to butylene, the alkylation indicators continuously improve.

Figure 2 – Results: With increasing isobutane to butylene ratio, alkylation performance continuously improves
Yield dependence of hydrocarbons C₈ (1) and C₉ (2) and higher

It has been established that the content of fraction C at a temperature of 80°C is the highest with the maximum content of target components – trimethylpentanes. In this case, the content of light (C₆-C₇) and heavy (C₉, and higher) fractions is minimal. This confirms the correctness of the conclusion about the optimality of the found temperatures.

The specificity of the alkylation of isobutane by butylenes is that the rate of the polymerization reaction, as noted, significantly exceeds the rate of alkylation. One of the methods to reduce polymerization is to create high ratios of isobutane and butylene in the reaction zone [6].

Findings

It has been established that alkylation at high ratios of reagents contributes to the suppression of the polymerization reaction, while the

range of butane dilution with isobutane ranges from 5 to 100:1. The study of alkylation under conditions of higher isobutane-to-butane ratios is challenging because it involves high reactant costs, especially conversion products, from non-reactive components.

In real sulfuric acid reactors, this ratio is very high, so it seemed expedient to study the nature of the alkylation reaction on a zeolite catalyst at isobutane:butene ratios approaching those in the process of sulfuric acid alkylation.

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